

THE LAUNCH OF WWFE-II: BENCHMARKING OF 3D STRENGTH AND DAMAGE THEORIES FOR POLYMER FIBRE

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ABSTRACT

Predicting the strength and deformation response of fibre reinforced composite materials under generalised conditions of lay-up and applied stress state is still the grand challenge for the composites research community. In 2004 the authors (together with Peter Soden) completed the first 'World-Wide Failure Exercise' (WWFE-I) which was aimed at benchmarking the status of current predictive techniques and to identify the magnitude of their shortfall. The present paper provides a strategy for building on the results of WWFE-I by proposing the launch of a second exercise of similar form, WWFE-II, thereby providing an impetus to the community such that the key theoretical deficiencies might be addressed. The paper is intended to trigger debate on the scope, choice and form of test problems that would be most applicable to validate and benchmark the latest theoretical candidates. Reliable test data are crucial to the success of the task and hence a plea for potential test cases backed by comprehensive data is made at the end of the paper.

Keywords: WWFE-II, triaxial, damage criteria, micro-cracks,

1 INTRODUCTION

Complex stresses are common in many civil and military applications of polymer composites. Examples include structures operating in deep water, the material in and around bolted joints, polymer composite components formed at elevated temperature (and therefore subject to residual stresses) and structures subjected to impact and blast loading. In general, therefore, 'real' composite structures have to resist three dimensional states of stress. Whilst this is readily understood by the composites community, there is a substantial gap between what we currently understand, and can model, and what design engineers would like to have (ie simple to use, structural analysis tools that are accurate under fully generalised conditions of material form and stress state).

Given the almost infinite permutations possible in fabricating a polymer composite component it is not unsurprising to find that there remain large gaps in our theoretical understanding. Until relatively recently, there has been an absence of any systematic study to determine the status of theoretical techniques for predicting the strength and deformation response of polymer composite structures. Put another way, the community didn't know where the gaps were or their magnitude. In 2004 the authors (together with Peter Soden) completed the first World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-I) to examine the status of failure criteria in fibre reinforced polymer composites. The work is fully documented through the publication of a book Ref[1].

WWFE-I was focused on continuous fibre, lamina based polymer composites subjected to uniaxial or biaxial states of stress - this being considered a sufficiently challenging step in its

own right. The study indeed proved to be a large and complex task, containing a detailed assessment of nineteen theoretical approaches and taking some 12 years to complete. There were many important outcomes but, in particular, the study highlighted significant shortfalls in predicting the strength and deformation response of polymer composite structures under biaxial states of stress. These shortfalls are discussed in greater detail later in the paper.

Given the passage of time since the start of WWFE-I (>12 years) and the still unfulfilled need of designers, the composites community finds itself in a somewhat similar position regarding the knowledge-base in 3-D stress predictive techniques ie currently, little faith exists in the accurate prediction of triaxial failure stresses, see Refs[1,26]. The authors perceive the need to launch the second World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II) to solve problems either not included or not satisfactorily dealt with in the first exercise. These include triaxial stresses and damage and delamination predictions in composites. Furthermore, the paper also provides a description of some of the available theories and activities dealing with damage mechanics and how to achieve a better way of validating and benchmarking some of the promising theories.

2 BACKGROUND TO WWFE-II

It is widely known that continuous fibre, lamina based, polymer composites have a propensity to develop micro cracks at an early stage of loading. These cracks can, in some circumstances, lead to the creation of delaminations (in-plane separation of the laminae), or to the formation in pressure vessels of a leakage path. However, composite structures containing micro cracks are often fully capable of carrying loads well beyond that at which the cracks were initiated. Fig 1 depicts a uni-axially loaded structure made of transparent glass/epoxy layers oriented at 0° and 90° relative to the vertical loading direction. The horizontal lines are formed by the evolution of transverse macro-cracks as the load increases in successive images from left to right.

Fig 1: Development of matrix cracks in $0/90^\circ$ glass/epoxy laminate, Ref[2].

As an example of crack density development in composites, Fig 2 shows how the measured crack density grows in the $0/90^\circ$ laminate (described above) as a function of the applied strain. The ratio between the occurrence of an ultimate failure (a structure broken into more the two pieces) and onset of initial damage could reach more than 50 in many typical structures, Ref[1]. Hence, it is important to have the means of predicting not only initial failure but also the manner in which damage progresses up to final fracture. Unfortunately, there is little consensus in the composite community concerning the level of maturity of the various theories to predict damage propagation in a generalised situation.

Fig 2 Variation of crack density with strain for a $0/90^\circ$ glass/epoxy laminate, Ref[2]

In almost all of the practical examples where fibre reinforced composites are employed in load bearing structures, 3-D stresses (e.g. geometric discontinuities such as fastener holes) are present and some form of allowance is made in the design process, even if

by empirical means. Certain techniques are under development, based on knowledge of the fracture toughness, where attempts are made to use material resistance (expressed in terms of Mode I, Mode II and Mode III parameters) to determine how induced damage might propagate and lead to a failure. However there is uncertainty as to how such techniques can be applied to generalised situations.

A classical example of the need to couple conventional and non-conventional failure theories is in the analysis of the structural behaviour of flat panel or a tube subjected to impact or a lateral indentation. Fig 3 shows the deformed shape of a thin-walled composite cylinder (tube) where a rigid indenter, simulating a heavy impact on a pipeline, has travelled vertically into the centre of the upper tube surface. Depending on material choice, layup configuration and tube geometry,

many modes of failure are possible. These include micro-cracking, delamination and buckling induced fibre failure. Such a test case illustrates the need to develop a more rigorous framework that could link the more macro laminate based failure criteria to the

Fig 3 A glass/epoxy composite thin walled tube subjected to lateral indentation, ref[19].

many fracture/damage growth based models that are appearing. In particular it seems that predicting the initiation of delamination damage is not well linked to predicting the propagation of delamination in composites laminates. The latter models assume that delaminations are already present whereas the former has had little attention paid to it.

As stated earlier, WWFE-I focused on the structural response under 2-D, in-plane states of stress. The study identified a number of issues, some of which were resolved during WWFE-I ('Status 1') and some that remained unresolved ('Status 2, 3') at its conclusion. These are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 A list of issues crucial for efficient use of composites

No	Case*	Issues addressed	Status
1	1 To 14	Use of micro-mechanics for prediction properties/failure	1
2	1 To 3	Prediction of the biaxial failure of a lamina in isolation	1
3	4 To 14	Prediction of 2D modes of failure	1
4	4 To 14	Prediction of the whole laminates failure envelopes	1
5	4 To 14	Matrix failure in tension, shear and compression	1
6	4 To 14	Single material non-linearity	1
7	4 To 14	Post failure modelling under 2D stresses	1
8	4 To 14	Prediction of fibre failure	1
9	1 To 14	<i>Thermal residual curing stress consideration</i>	2
10	4 To 14	<i>In situ strength of an embedded lamina</i>	2
11	4 To 14	<i>Leakage of pressurised pipes</i>	2
12	4 To 14	<i>Multiple material and structural non-linearities</i>	2
13	6,9,14	<i>Thin and thick laminae</i>	2
14	4 To 14	<i>Effects of lay up sequence</i>	2
15	9,10,14	<i>Prediction of large deformation</i>	2
16		<i>3D failure criteria and stress systems</i>	2

17		<i>Delamination initiation and propagation</i>	2
18		<i>Effects of other matrix and reinforcement materials</i>	2
19		<i>Other forms of fibre reinforcement, woven and non- woven cloths</i>	2
20		<i>Effects of ply thickness and stacking sequence</i>	2
21		<i>Sequential loading, e.g. compression after impact, leak after impact</i>	2
22		<i>Monotonic loading, unloading and reloading</i>	2
23		Integration of structural failure and specimen design	3
24		Failure under stress gradient	3
25		Buckling in thin walled and slender structures	3
26		Long-term behaviour, creep, relaxation, fatigue	3
27		Environmental effects, including moisture and aggressive substances	3
28		Effects of high and low and temperatures	3

* See Ref[1] for details of the Test Cases

Fig 4 A schematic of a composite lamina under a triaxial state of stress. $\pm\sigma_1$ Longitudinal, $\pm\sigma_2$: Transverse, $\pm\sigma_3$: Through-thickness direct stresses and τ_{12} : In-plane, τ_{13} : Transverse and τ_{23} : Through-thickness shear stresses.

the failure behaviour of a large combination of stresses. A general loading of a lamina involves the application of six different stress components as shown in Fig 4. These stresses could be applied in six different states

State (1): Uniaxial stress: $+\sigma_1, -\sigma_1, +\sigma_2, -\sigma_2, +\sigma_3, -\sigma_3, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}, \text{OR } \tau_{23}$.

State(2): Biaxial stress: Any two combination of two stresses, e.g $-\sigma_3, \tau_{12}$.

State(3): Any combination of three stresses, e.g. $-\sigma_3, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}$.

State(4): Any combination of four stresses, e.g. $+\sigma_1, -\sigma_2, +\sigma_3, \tau_{12}$.

State(5): Any combination of five stresses, e.g. $+\sigma_1, +\sigma_2, +\sigma_3, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}$.

State(6): Any combination of six stresses, e.g. $-\sigma_1, -\sigma_2, -\sigma_3, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}, \tau_{23}$

In total, 215 different sets of stresses may be

Recognising the fact that a tremendous amount of effort will be required to address all of the unresolved design issues, the authors have applied a prioritisation. We aim to launch the second World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II) to address those issues at Status 2. They are all related to triaxial stresses, damage and fracture mechanics.

In order to illustrate the added complexity of WWFE-II in relation to that of WWFE-I, let us first consider the 3-D stress interactions within a composite.

A full characterisation of composites requires a thorough understanding of

Fig 5 Combinations of stress cases not attempted in WWFE-I

applied to a lamina and these sets are distributed among the above six states of stresses as illustrated Fig 5. The figure shows the number of sets attempted in the WWFE-I by some of the theories in relation to the ideal number of sets. Clearly, these sets are much less than those needed to fully characterise the 3D behaviour of a lamina. The small number is largely attributed to a lack of Test Cases representing the through-thickness stress ($\pm\sigma_3$, τ_{23}). Effectively, the WWFE-II aims, among others, at identifying and reconciling those theories that are capable of modelling failure under the nine combinations of stress in State(6) with available experimental data. Ideally, the same theories should give equivalent capability of modelling failure under other states of stress, if the underlying assumptions, be it phenomenological or otherwise, that govern State(6) did not fall apart when applied to States (2), (3), (4) or (5).

3 POTENTIAL THEORIES FOR WWFE-II

One of the first steps in starting WWFE-II is to identify those theories that are capable of handling and incorporating advanced aspects of three dimensional states of stress in polymer composites, including through-thickness stresses, micro-cracks, crack density formation, delamination and fracture toughness parameters. There is a huge body of publications dealing with these issues, including, typically, the individuals and research groups listed in Table 2. These, taken in conjunction with the contributors to WWFE-I, constitute a significant body that will form the starting point for the organisers in seeking out participants.

Table 2: A list of some of the world-wide groups who are contributing to the current state-of-the-art in the field of damage and fracture mechanics in composites.

Group	Expertise and contribution
Smith and Ogin (Surrey Uni, UK)[18]	Pioneering work in understanding of cracking in composites under various types of loads (bending, open hole etc..).
Cantwell (Liverpool Uni, UK)[24]	Damage in plates, panels and shells under impact.
Hine and Duckett (Leeds University, UK)[20]	High pressure testing up to 850MPa. The facility is useful for development of triaxial test data.
Soutis (Sheffield Uni, UK)[16]	Developing models for matrix cracking and combined matrix cracking and delamination.
Li, Reid, Soden (Manchester Uni, UK)[3,19]	Continuum damage mechanics modelling for crack development in multi-directional laminates. They also included delamination in their model.
Fleck (Cambridge Uni, UK),[30]	Modelling composites with cracks, Kink failure, open hole etc...
Christensen, Deteresa, Springer (Stanford Uni,USA) [4,12,14]	Published well-recognised papers in the area of experimental and theoretical analyses on high pressure and triaxial failure of composites.
Nairn (University of Utah, USA)[31]	Application of variational or finite mechanics analysis for predicting initiation and propagation of matrix micro-cracking
Talreja (USA)[17]	Continuum damage mechanics (CDM) with micromechanics to predict the crack density and stiffness reduction. Fatigue of composites.
Camanho and D'ávila (NASA, USA)[25]	Numerical analysis of damage and delamination
O'Brien (NASA, USA)[13]	Measurement of the fracture toughness in composites and the prediction of delamination in composites.
Badaliance etal(NRL, USA)[33]	Use of Dissipated Energy Density (DED)
Hashin (USA)[23]	Pioneered earlier work of 3D failure criteria for the prediction of failure in a lamina and his equations are embedded in a number of software. .
Gosse (Boeing, USA)[32]	Application of strain invariant failure theory. Theory formulated on a micro-mechanics level and uses a finite element package.
Poursartip with Vaziri and Williams (U B C, Canada)[22]	The group has made efforts to apply a damage mechanics to the prediction of deformation and failure under static and impact loadings.
Kruger and Konig (University of Stuttgart, Germany)[9]	They have worked in the area of application of finite element package to predict the delamination in multi-directional laminates.
Johnson (DLR, Germany)[10]	Employed numerical packages to analyse the initiation and development of delamination under impact loadings

Hermann (Universitat Paderborn, Germany)[11]	Theoretical work on the transverse matrix cracking and its induced local delamination in laminates containing angle plies.
Henaff-Gardin, Lafaries-Fernot, Ousset (France)[5,7].	Characteristic damage variables, delamination of layered composites
Rebiere (Universite du Maine) and Gamby (ENSMA, France)[8]	Experimental and analytical work on the evolution of transverse cracking, longitudinal cracking and delamination in cross ply laminates.
P. Ladeveze (E.N.S. de Cachan/Universite, France)[15]	Bridging micro- and mesoscales damage in laminated composites and to the effect of out-of-plan stresses on the behaviour of composites.
Zinoviev and Tsvetkov (Russia)[21]	Data for the behaviour of composite rings and tubes under large hydrostatic pressure, reaching 500MPa.

The list covers a wide spectrum of the composite community, including theoreticians, experimentalists, engineers, designers and modellers. The authors invite theoreticians, designers, industrialist and academia to get in touch if they have a distinct theory or model capable of dealing with the issues suggested in the WWFE-II, and who wish to participate.

4 POTENTIAL TEST CASES

One of the most important aspects of validating and benchmarking failure theories is the use of representative and accurate experimental data of the highest pedigree. Previous experience by the authors, gained from the WWFE-I, highlighted the difficulty in identifying & collecting data from reputable research institutions and research groups around the world. In WWFE-I the issue was resolved through adverts in a number of journal and international gatherings, followed by detailed discussions with those institutes that did offer data (usually accomplished through visits and meetings). In addition, a significant proportion of the data sets were generated and provided by the authors, see Refs[27-28]. However, as the WWFE-I progressed and the theories were probed deeply, inadequacies in the test data surfaced in a number of areas. The experimental results were like a set of Russian dolls where some participants were content with the information provided, representing the outer dolls. What was clear was that a more robust assessment of the predictive capabilities requires information about the very inner doll(s). There was, for instance, a dearth of information pertaining to the definition of initial failure stresses, cracks initiation, effects of thermal residual stresses on the laminate studied etc., see Table 1 and Chapter 7 in Ref[1] for more details about the shortcomings of the WWFE-I.

We (the organisers) seek to obtain ‘good’ test data covering areas of triaxial stresses, damage and delamination areas, listed in Table 1 under Status 2, to validate and benchmark the WWFE-II theories. We invite experimentalists and research laboratories around the world to send their data to us and to comment on the validity of the test cases suggested in the WWFE-II. The data must include all the information about the materials, material manufacturing, material testing, all measurements, fibre volume fraction, voids, accurate observation, data processing, calibration, failure stresses an strain throughout the loading route etc... The data could describe one or more sets of the cases listed in Table 3. The first six cases are considered to be crucial for establishing the maturity of the 3D material failure models whereas the last 5 cases incorporate additional structural modelling.

Table 3 A list of potential cases for the WWFE-II.

No	Details	Data needed
1	Biaxial and triaxial stresses (including through thickness stresses and hydrostatic pressure).	Biaxial and traixial compression up to 2GPa pressure, unloading, combined in-plane and through-thickness loadings
2	Pure Mode I, Pure Mode II, Pure Mode III and a combination of these modes.	Load-deflection, deformed shape, strains, failure description upon loading and re-loading
3	Effects of ply thickness ($0^\circ_n/90^\circ_m$ and $\pm\phi^\circ/90^\circ_n$)	Matrix crack density in all plies at various

	laminates).	loads
4	Through-thickness compression of various laminates (e.g. 0°/90°, +55°/-55°, Quasi-isotropic).	Stress, strain curves, modes of failure.
5	Unloading and reloading under complex stresses of various laminates (e.g. 0°, 0°/90°, +45°/-45°, ±φ°/90° _n).	Stress strain curves, details of damage occurrence and development
6	Thermal stresses effects	Measurement of residual stresses in room and elevated temperature cured composites
7	Leakage of pressurised thin tubes.	Pressure, strains, fractography before and after leakage
8	Laminate with central open hole under biaxial loads.	Loads, strain, stresses, failure details, fractography.
9	Beam under three point bend test (e.g. 0°/90° lay-up).	Load, deflection, strains, failure details at various loads
10	Lateral indentation of panels and tubes.	Load-deflection, deformed shape, strains, failure description, unloading and re-loading.
11	Strength of impacted plates (or tubes).	Effect of impact parameters on the strength

5 FORMAT OF THE EXERCISE

Following the footsteps and the success of WWFE-I , see Refs[27-29] and Chapter1 in ref[1], it is anticipated that the WWFE-II would run in two parts; Part A and Part B. A set of instructions will be sent to the invited players. These instructions include the following

- The organisers will provide the contributors with material properties (e.g. elastic constants, strengths and stress-strain curves etc..) for selected composite materials. Additional information would also be provided on request (subject to availability).
- The contributors will be asked to predict the failure strengths and deformation at all stages of failure under a range of biaxial and triaxial loads and also to predict the form of the stress-strain curves.
- The contributors will be asked to present their results as failure envelopes and stress-strain curves in a specified graphical and tabular formats, sent to them by the organisers, and to grant permission/ copyright for the results and the contributions to be superimposed on other results (e.g. experimental on theoretical) and published in suitable and convenient forms.
- Existing experimental results will to be superimposed on the theoretical predictions and the superimposed graphs sent back to the contributors with tables of the experimental results.
- Each contributor would write two papers.
 - (a) The first paper (Part A) would describe their failure theory and method of application to laminates in sufficient detail to allow their predictions to be reproduced by others, comment on the nature and effects of the failure predicted and, if appropriate, how the predictions could be used for design. This first paper would be submitted with 'blind' theoretical predictions.
 - (b) The second paper (Part B) would present graphs of the theoretical results compared with experimental data and any comments the contributor wished to make on the correlation between experiment and theory. The contributor may choose to add a figure (or figures) to demonstrate refinement or particular features of their approach.

Details of what the two parts would contain are as follows:

PART A would contain:-

- A detailed specification of a series of Test Cases and a format for presenting the predictions, chosen by the organisers to stretch the failure theories to the full.
- A series of invited papers from originators of the foremost failure theories available at the present time (or their chosen colleagues). The papers would provide a comprehensive and detailed description of the theory employed, and would contain predictions of strength and stress/strain curves for each Test Case, using the data provided.

- A direct comparison, by the organisers, of the methodologies employed in each theory and of the predictions made for each test case.

PART B would contain:-

- Detailed experimental results for each of the test cases and a full description of how the experiments were conducted.
- A second paper from each participant, containing a graphical comparison of their original prediction with the experimental results for each test case, comments on the performance of their chosen theory, and the opportunity to show refinements in the light of the experimental data.
- An overall comparison of the theories represented in the exercise against the experimental results, presented in such a form that their degree of validity (or otherwise) could be judged by the community.
- Shortfalls in the theories and in the experiments, highlighted by the 'exercise'.

The adoption of the two-part approach will allow both a 'blind test' and a further opportunity for participants to offer refinements to the theories, thereby advancing the science. The process of publication will be such that no participant was in receipt of the experimental data until **all** of the 'blind prediction' papers (i.e. the Part A submissions) had been completed and are with the publishers in their final revised form. Consequently, Part A would be published before Part B.

It is anticipated that each part of the exercise would take around 18 months to be completed. Shorter periods could be achieved if the invited participants adhered to the deadlines and the instructions set by the organisers. The participants should also note that each paper will be subjected to a very stringent reviewing process before its final acceptance for publication. The process may require a number of iterations, reaching up to five.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

There is currently a sizeable amount of fragmented activities related to the behaviour of composite under three-dimensional state of stress. These activities have not been co-ordinated and hence the boundaries of their applicability remain largely unknown.

The paper has provided a description of the initial stages aimed launching the second world-wide failure exercise by the authors to cover damage and science-based failure criteria and their application to real structures.

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